

The Role of Allegation Example in the Beauty of Pashto Language Poem

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ABSTRACT: *This research aims to determine the significant role of allegation example literary term in the beauty of poem. For this purpose, the research is carried out as a library-based research, which involves the step-by-step process used to gather information from different relevant literary books. The findings show that this literary term is completed based on the simile which is generally a compound simile. The poet makes a claim in monostich (a single verse) of his poem and in another monostich, he presents an accepted fact as an argument for the stability of his claim. It is not necessary that the claim be in the first half of the verse, the argument may come in the first half of the verse and then the claim may be made. The findings also revealed that this literary term, in addition to beautifying the poem and increasing the chances of acceptance, helps the poet to prove an impossible thing through artistic reasoning. The findings perhaps help the poets regarding their claim how to prove an impossible thing; and the poet make a possible claim to the point of one hundred percent agreement on artistic reasoning.*

Keywords: allegation example, poetry, aesthetic aspect, possible claim, impossible claim.

I. INTRODUCTION

Our art books are mostly traditional. Art is used in poem, of course poem becomes beautiful with it and this is necessary with poem, because if there is no art in poetry, beauty escapes from it. That fact must be taken into account that not every art and term is studied in the mentioned books. Maybe there have been some efforts lately and these less efforts are great efforts and initiative for this explaining this literary term. For this purpose, I decided to explore one of the most important and interesting literary terms which is allegation example literary term among the other significant literary terms. Thus, I would like to highlight its aesthetic aspects. According to Dermal (2016), the aesthetic aspects of the allegation example literary term are the best examples of short parables or allegorical simile.

The fact is that the allegation example literary term is mostly a type of short allegories. But not every allegorical poem is allegation example literary term. This study is almost new to other studies, as it focuses on the role of the allegation example literary term in the beauty and value of poem. It is a library-based research and uses an

explanatory method for which many reliable books been studied regarding the topic. And then after the critique, the scope for innovation is taken.

Research Question

The present study aimed to address the following research question:

What is the role of allegation example literary term in the beauty of poem?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Haqpal (2010) states that the allegation example literary term is a meaningful literary term, in which the poet brings a matter in one monostich and gives an example in another monostich to prove it. Similarly, Pacha (2004) points out that Ali Khan a poet of Pashto language has discussed that my friend's character became bad by instigation of my rival. Because my friend lives with my rival. By living there, he changed his old good character into bad. He also gives an example and adds when the shows are created fit, but when it comes to crooked legs, the fit shows would be crooked.

Furthermore, Ali Kham and Hamkar (2015, p. 146) argue to prove his claim in the verse below.

*“At the point of the rival, the good mood of friend turned out to be bad /
Eventually the shows will be bent by crooked legs”.*

*“Do well to those who do bad with you/ Every palm that bears fruit is
stoned”*

Based on the above line, it is a common adage in our society that a tree that bears fruit is stoned. Or the person who works is criticized by people. Although it is clearly stated in our Sharia verses that it is better to do good than to do evil. But Rahman Baba wisely admits this to us and gives an example of his claim that the fruit tree does against evil. Because people throw stones at it and it throws fruit to them.

There are usually two separate issues relating to allegation example literary term, which are compared to each other in the form of similitude, and the poet wants to prove each other on the basis of simile and similitude. In the above verse, it is a different matter to do good against evil, but to prove this point, the poet discusses a different issue in the form of similitude and similarities, such as with a tree who does evil and throws stones at it and it throws fruit to them instead. These are two separate issues, which stand side by side in resemblance to each other. Allegation example literary term is a great feature of the Indian style, which is very popular among poets of this style. But this literary term is not limited to Indian poets' style and has been used by other poets of the classical period as well (Hewadmal, 2000).

Khalil (2005, p.361) argues that we can see an example of this in the poetry of Rahman Baba who is a well-known poet of Pashto language.

*“Treasure increases generously/When the well water is drawn can be
increased”*

The use of the allegation example literary term in the ancient poetry of Pashto literature is very much. On the contrary, its examples are rarely found in contemporary Poetry.

The Value and Aesthetic Aspect of the Allegation Example Literary Term in Poem

In our art books mostly the allegation example literary term is known, but it is not discussed, how much do the allegation example literary term value and play role in the beauty of poem? Most of the time the authors have only known it and besides that they have given just a few examples with analysis. The term has also traditionally been known to follow one another. It is also said everywhere that the poet makes a claim or a

meaning in one and a half verses and brings an example or parable in another to prove it. It is not important that the poet make a claim first and then prove it by example. Sometimes it happens that the poet first gives an example and then puts his claim before us after the example. The given example is an accepted fact in the society and the poet wants to express and prove it. As in the following verse, Shaida a poet of Pashto language first gives an accepted example and then extends his claim to prove it.

Khalil (2014, p.165) argues the poem of Shaida,

*“Always a soft wood is food of worm/May Shaida not be the man empty of
politics”*

Worms usually eat wood that is soft in the middle. A human should not be as soft as the soft wood and they should be less hard and bitter. The basis of the allegation example literary term is often based on simile, and this simile is often a composite simile or there may be several tenors and vehicles in a verse. But the comparators (“as”, “like”, “then”) do not come with it, and besides, the allegation example literary term is mostly birth of an artistic environment, in which a few significant beauties join hands and prove the possible and the impossible speak.

Baryalai (1999, p.105) argues the poem of Abdul GhafarAhar who is another famous poet of Pashto language

*“The vein tepidity love with the string of Patience/Lion cannot be fasten
with nose-ring”*

In the above single verse love is tenor to a lion and patience is to a string. The poet expresses that when I tighten the lion of love with the patience string. So, it's like to fasten a lion with a nose-ring and it is impossible. The beauty of the allegation example literary term in the poem is revealed here, that the poet has presented an interesting and accepted fact to prove his point.

On the aesthetic side of poem, the allegation example literary term is that when a poet proves his claim on the basis of an accepted fact, his argument will be artistic. But the poet will reinforce his point in such a way that the audience will accept it without hesitation. Lovers always shout at their stony-heart loved ones, but when the banality is replaced with innovation, the same phenomenon must be explained in a new way with a new argument. Then the argument would be that no matter how much one cries for love, it is difficult to cleanse his heart and accept his lover. It is like a person pouring cold water on an oiled vessel, and an oiled vessel is not cleaned no matter how much cold water is passed through it.

Similarly, Darwish (2018, p. 34) states in his poem

*“Your tears will not affect your heart/For how long will you pass cold
water in this oiled vessel”*

His argument is based on a commonly accepted fact and he has put forward an interesting claim for this argument as we see in his second single verse. He has pointed to the similarities between tears and cold water. It is fact that the oiled vessel cannot be cleaned with cold water as the tears do not affect stony heart of one's love.

The allegation example literary term's value in poem is that the poet mostly shows possible things aesthetically. Similarly, he made the impossible things possible in a very sweet and gentle language, which we not only dare to reject, but also we accept them without hesitation. When everyone treats us badly, but when they come to us and fall on our feet, then it is a demand of religion and Pashtunism that we will not deal with it and we feel safe that there is no problem between us. Samim (2007) argues that Hamid Baba a famous poet of Pashto language wants to make that possible speak impossible, so for this we need a reason to accept it. Hamid Baba proves it in his poem and tells us:

*“Don't be proud if enemy falls himself on your feet/Because of the flood
kissing the wall fell down.”*

in this poem Hamid Baba prove it that if the enemy falls to his feet, do not feel safe. He has pointed to the similarities between enemy which falls himself on your foot and the flood which damages the wall (the flood reaches on its foot and then it fell down the wall).

When grievances and frustrations abound in friendship, the friendship become distant. Orakzai (200, p.401) mentions that Mumtaz another poet of Pashto language does not accept it and says the bond of friendship and camaraderie becomes stronger and more enjoyable when the friends make a lot of complaints about one another. In fact, it is not really possible. Because as the grief grows, so does the heartbreak and distance. But Mumtaz says no! With that comes the friendship become more enjoyable. If we do not agree with it, then he metaphorically brings us an accepted fact, and the fact is that when cotton clothes are wrinkled, they become more beautiful. Furthermore, Mumtaz adds in his verse:

*“Friendships, however, are beautiful with complaints/Cotton clothes
become beautiful with wrinkles”.*

One of the great values of allegation example literary term in poetry is that it increases the chances of acceptance of the poet's speech. The allegation example literary term is a rational argument to prove the poet's statement. We say fire can be lighted from your skirt. Or when someone in the family is smart and hardworking, the responsibilities fell down on his shoulders and faces much problems. But if we want to prove this wisely, then the example of spring is enough. When the fruit is ripened in the branch, it bends the branch back and would be loaded with it:

*“Smart people want their own people /The branches are burdened with
ripened fruit”*

In the same way, another famous poet of Pashto language Karwan wants to prove us that the heart is that time heart, alive and fragrant when red tears are shed over it, and the sad heart of a friend would be that which cries for friend. The heart which does not cry for friend is not a heart. The heart that cries for love is really a heart because the pearl is a pearl when it has water and when the water is gone, if it is a pearl, then its value and importance are gone. Furthermore, Karwan (2016, p.292) argues in a single verse of his poem:

*“The color and fragrance with red tears has red rose heart/ The value of a
pearl is when it has water”.*

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to Creswell (2014), researchers have the freedom to choose the research methods they prefer. Though, researchers are expected to state the reasons for choosing a particular method over other methods. However, the method chosen must match the purpose of research and match the study questions. This is a library-based study, using a descriptive method. The data regarding the topic has been collected from reliable sources. And I have placed the product and result of my mind in this research as well.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the beauty of poem, allegation example literary term plays a very important role. Unfortunately, in our art books much of the focus have been on identifying the allegation example literary term and bringing up its few examples. In addition to the identifying and examples, it needs to be clarified, what is the role of the allegation example literary term in the beauty, acceptance and value of the poem and what are the benefits of using it in the poem. Therefore, I collected the data from the credible books to describe the role of allegation example literary

term in the beauty of poem. The findings show the poet makes an interesting, new, logical and artistic argument for the proof of his claim, which is usually in the form of simile and allegory and makes an artistic proportion and environment in the poem. On the basis of this argument, the poet strengthens a possible claim based on an accepted fact, and makes an impossible claim possible, which has a very good chance of acceptance.

V. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to collect information from different reliable books about the role of plaintiff-like literary term in poem. The use of allegation example literary term which is a meaningful literary term in poem adds beauty and value to poem and increases the chances of acceptance for impossible things. The findings show that the allegation example literary term is often based on a compound analogy, which evokes spiritual sweetness and beauty in a poem. The use of allegation example literary term in poem is so sweet and artistic that it makes impossible phenomena as possible

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